

PSYchiatric disorders and COMorbidities caused by pollution in the MEDiterranean area (PsyCoMed)

Original proposal for Data Management Plan

Open science practices and Data Management Plan

The coordinator, UBx, is committed to a comprehensive and resolute policy in the service of scientific advances and societal issues with a **roadmap for open science** as one of the pillars of UBx's strategy for 2025 (U25) and 2030 (U30). This strategic plan aims to **rethink the subscription models for digital resources, to strongly support new editorial methods in favour of open access, to initiate and promote good practices in the management of research data, to be a stakeholder in citizen and participatory science and to support all open science practices through appropriate training**. PsyCoMed will adhere to this Open Science policy and research by the staff members will **follow the EC Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information, the revised Public Sector Information Directive, and the EU Copyright directive**. This will foster reliability (through better verification), reproducibility, and ensure better sharing of resources as well as being more responsive to society's needs. In line with the Open Science ambitions of the EC, PsyCoMed will furthermore ensure **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) and open data sharing** with the help of OSKAR Bordeaux, as well as adhere to the commonly agreed standards of **scientific integrity**. Scientific integrity will be carefully controlled via the WP8 Ethics. **OSKAR (Open Science Knowledge ARchive)** Bordeaux is the open institutional interoperable warehouse of UBx and its partners and aims to support the open science movement and offer an alternative to dominant business editorial models. OSKAR Bordeaux makes it possible **to host, preserve, promote and make accessible all types of scientific publications of the Bordeaux site's research community**. OSKAR is searchable by other warehouses and all regulations related to data-sharing will be included in the Data Management Plan (see below). This implies that research dissemination and communication materials (data, physical samples, analysis strategies, publications, etc.) are **accessible to all levels of society**. It also implies that **knowledge sharing is transparent** through collaborative networks and that open-notebook science is practiced. In short, a practice of science allowing collaboration and contribution of others through freely available materials and enabling reproduction (and re-use) of the research data and methods. PsyCoMed will focus on helping the (exchanged) staff members gain knowledge and skills to implement an Open Science policy through dedicated training when necessary. Table 5 summarizes the actions taken to comply with the open science practices under Horizon Europe and in line with local roadmaps.

We strongly believe that giving open access to our scientific publications will speed up important breakthroughs by European researchers which consequently will strengthen European Research and Innovation and lead to boosting knowledge and competitiveness in Europe. Altogether, PsyCoMed's Open Science strategy, via the usage of the EOSC,

OSKAR and other trusted repositories, will limit waste of resources, accelerate innovation advancements through reusable and reproducible results, enable increased reliability and efficiency of research and will create more trust in science. It furthermore facilitates cross-disciplinary research and inclusion of all relevant actors (including citizens), thereby leading to more creativity and greater impacts.

Open science practice	Action
Open access to scientific publications	Open peer review for publications, open access publications, and/or deposit in open data-bases and OSKAR for all articles issued by the consortium. E.g. through OpenAIRE ⁹⁴ initiative
FAIR data management	Application of FAIR principles through deposit in open data-bases and through the production (and regular update) of a Data Management Plan (DMP). Train researchers on the importance of proper data use so it is retraceable, reproducible and available to the consortium and to the larger community when possible.
Reproducibility of research outputs	Transparent research design, robustness of statistical analyses, addressing negative results, quality control mechanisms. Deposition in Horizon Europe/open repository; Open and early sharing of research outputs through pre-registration, registered reports, pre-prints, crowd-sourcing, etc. Considering digital blue prints. Training of the researchers in open sharing practices (as member of international ‘Reproducibilitea’ action) without violating protected IP of partners.
Digital or physical access to project outputs	Using European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), access to physical results through deposit/provision upon request in relevant biobanks/collections. Deposit of data supporting the publications and information about the research outputs/tools/instruments needed to validate scientific publication conclusions or to validate/reuse research data, in a trusted repository (latest at the time of publication). A project factsheet and website.
Immediate open access in case of public emergency	In case of emergency (e.g. pollution crisis in the Mediterranean basin), immediate access will be given to the repositories where publications and research outputs are stored
Citizen, civil society and end-user engagement	Co-design activities (with policy makers, society at large, and inclusion activities with young people), cocreation activities (with industry), co-assessment activities (e.g. monitoring/evaluating for other projects/programmes), outreach activities (e.g. Pint of Science), booths at stakeholders’ events, pressreleases, social media updates and participation in radio debates/exchanges.

1.2.5. Research data management and management of other research outputs

In order to maximise the effectiveness and reproducibility of the data/research outputs, the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ will be followed. For efficient dissemination of results, a **Data Management Plan (DMP) in line with the FAIR principles** will be established within the first 6 months of the project (Deliverable 1.3 & 7.2) (**Table 6**). The DMP will be consistent with the intellectual property right (IPR) policy to be defined in the Consortium Agreement and updated as any changes occur in the consortium, curation and/or legal policies. In particular, the DMP will include the following core elements: 1. Data summary (description and collection or re-use of existing data); 2. FAIR data (Documentation and data quality); 3. Other research outputs (Storage and backup during the research process); 4. Data management responsibilities and allocation of resources; 5. Data security (sharing and long-term preservation); 6. Legal and ethical requirements, codes of conduct. To provide secure access and a clear context to the research output, thereby enhancing their findability and potential reuse, standardized metadata frameworks and trusted

repositories will be used. A data management team is available at UBx and assigned to assure proper execution and follow-up of the data management plan.

Type of data	Findability of data	Accessibility of data	Interoperability of data	Reusability of data	Curation & storage
Source code	Public repository (e.g. GitHub)	Open access	Open and wellused packages (e.g. Python, ImageJ, Matlab)	Software will be accompanied with test data to ensure reusability	UBx Data Management Team
Experimental data (incl. images, numerical data and databases)	Public repository (Zenodo, Figshare, etc.)	IP protection for relevant innovations (through science transfer offices), but data will not be withhold from open access. In case of patents, procedures will be planned in such a way that publications don't need to be delayed	Data deposited in open formats and software (where possible) such as .txt, .fasta, .csv, .tiff and accompanied by standardized metadata and README file. English language will be used	Repositories with clearly described conditions of use (typically under a Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal (CC0 1.0) Public Domain Dedication, a Creative Commons Attribution (CCBY) or an ODC Public Domain Dedication and Licence, with a material transfer agreement (when applicable). The corresponding persistent identifier can be cited for interested parties re-using the data	
Biological material (incl. cell and animal models and their derivatives, human materials)	Local archives and public repositories such as Addgene, JAX, etc.	Biological material will be shared upon simple request following publication, unless we identify valuable IP, in which case we will first protect commercial exploitation, either through patenting or via a material transfer agreement (MTA) that restricts the material from commercial use.	Generation of Research Resource Identifiers (RRIDs)	A Material Transfer Agreement (and a non-disclosure agreement if applicable) will be concluded with the beneficiaries in order to clearly describe the types of reuse that are permitted	